

CURRENT ISSUES OF ADAPTATION OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS TO SCHOOL LIFE

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the problem of creating adoration for children to the school regime has been identified as an important and pressing problem of child psychology, pedagogy and age-related physiology, the inseparable links between thinking, intelligence and emotional processes in Special Studies, the level of emotional development is directly affected by the formation of personal qualities, the intellectual and social development of the individual.

Keywords: Adaptation period, activity, life situation, school age, didactic games, educational achievements, school year, Social, Psychological, physiologic.

АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ АДАПТАЦИИ МЛАДШИХ ШКОЛЬНИКОВ К ШКОЛЬНОЙ ЖИЗНИ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье проблема формирования адаптации детей к школьному режиму рассматривается как важная и актуальная проблема детской психологии, педагогики и возрастной физиологии, в специальных исследованиях выявлены тесные связи между мышлением, интеллектом и эмоциональными процессами, высказаны мнения о том, что уровень эмоционального развития оказывает непосредственное влияние на формирование личностных качеств, интеллектуальное и социальное развитие личности.

Ключевые слова: Период адаптации, активность, жизненная ситуация, школьный возраст, дидактические игры, образовательные достижения, учебный год, социальные, психологические, физиологические.

The current period, when the development of Science and technology in the new Uzbekistan is reaching its peak, puts very important demands on each member of society. Especially waiting for developments, updates and quality changes in education [1]. In this sense, reforms and achievements in the direction of education and education

for educators operating in the system of continuing education, the problem of adaptation of Primary School students is currently relevant. Adaptation is the natural life of a person, which manifests itself in adaptation (habituation) to new living conditions. New events, new social ties, new social roles... the meaning of the period of entry into an unusual period for children is a life situation. This is manifested in the fact that not only the success of mastering educational activities, but also the convenience of being at school, the health of the child, his attitude to school and studies depend on his well-being.

It is necessary to create psychological and pedagogical conditions that provide a favorable course of adaptation of first-graders to school education.

The main indicators of a child's comfortable adaptation: physical, mental and positive health establish contact with children, with a teacher; formation of adequate behavior, mastering the skills of educational activities.

An indicator of the complexity of the school adaptation process is negative changes in the child's behavior: it can be excessive excitement, even aggression, or, conversely, latergy, depression. Feelings of fear, unwillingness to go to school, etc. can arise.

Between the ages of 6-7, a new stage begins. Social development the child he tries to get out of bounds, preschool age ... at this stage, the dominant role of the family is characteristic in satisfying the material communicative and emotional needs of the child. Therefore, work with future first graders begins precisely with acquaintance with the family [2]. This happens long before the child becomes a first grader.

Admission to school is associated with the need to adapt the child to changed living conditions. Adaptation to an educational institution occurs at 3 levels: physiological, social and correct psychological.

Psychological adaptation is determined by the activity of the individual and implies not only the "absorption" of the minor into the new social system, but also some changes. The most important condition for successful adaptation is a combination of adaptation and adaptive activity, which varies depending on the situation. In the first months of children's stay at school, new forms of the child's relationship with the world and himself, stable methods of interaction with peers and adults are formed, and the directions of personal self-awareness are determined at school. During the period of adaptation to an educational institution, a social and intellectual basis is created for the further education and development of the child. The success of adapting children to school conditions is largely due to the formation of educational motivation, a positive emotional attitude towards the teacher and classmates to the school, a high level of voluntary regulation of behavior and cognitive processes. Personal

characteristics of students and relationships with parents also play an important role in the process of school adaptation.

Physiological adaptation of first graders. Studies lead to radical changes in the child's lifestyle, including physical. It is common for a child to sit in the same place for a long time, there is no normal physical activity and freedom of movement. It is important to organize the regime of days correctly, to replace loads more often [3]. The correct Organization of the transition period from the game state depends on the skill of the teacher.

If physiological adaptation proceeds in the same automatic way, the situation is different with socio-psychological adaptation: this is an active adaptation process. Adaptation of a child to school is not a one-sided process: not only new conditions affect the child, but he himself is trying to change the socio-psychological situation, trying not only to "integrate" into it, but also to "unify" it.

Social characteristics of school adaptation of first graders.

The child's adaptation to the new collective, learning to communicate, the problems of the people who appeared and the resolution of conflicts. It is necessary to properly treat the child with difficulties in communication and help to overcome them.

A child who enters school suddenly does not become a schoolboy. Formation, entry into school life occurs during primary school, and the combination of the characteristics of preschool childhood with the characteristics of a schoolboy characterizes the entire period of primary school age. All children who begin their schooling experience certain difficulties, and the success of the child's social activities will depend on how well the adaptation period went during school admission [4].

Analysis of the process of school adaptation of first graders allows you to distinguish the following forms:

Adaptation of the body to new conditions of life and activity, physical, intellectual stress, where success depends on the age of the child, his level of training; on the level of formation of morphofunctional systems of the body; the level of development of voluntary regulation of the child's behavior and school; on how the situation in the family has changed.

Adaptation to the new social relationships and connections exist to a greater extent to spatial time relationships (maintaining daily routine, school supplies, school uniforms).

Every teacher who works in the first grade of elementary school should keep in mind that the aspirations of children to acquire knowledge are determined by several factors that are successfully pedagogically competent in them. The educational environment corresponds to the psychological and physiological characteristics and capabilities of first graders. Reading first graders should be based on the peculiarities

of organizing the activities of children in the seventh year of life. Special attention is paid to the teacher. It is important to remember that the first days of children's stay in school are associated with the peculiarities of the psyche of such qualities as carelessness of individual children, quick distraction of annoyance, lack of self-control. Therefore, it is very important not to speak harshly to children.(especially during the adaptation period). Try to focus on the positive views of the students so as not to pull them back.

In the educational process, it is important to take into account the individual characteristics of children. At the beginning of the training, the teacher should provide each child with the opportunity to work at his discretion. Absolutely unacceptable, faster at this time! Delay everyone! etc.K phrases should not be said. The loads of schoolchildren should gradually increase.

The level of development and formation of functional systems mental processes children (attention, memory, thinking, arbitrary level), ensuring educational success, determines the need to give children educational assignments of varying complexity, and this, in particular, gives the teacher a different share of their participation in the implementation. The teacher should know that many children of this age can complete assignments only with the help of adults who require a sequence of actions. This is not a negative characteristic of the student, but reflects the age and individual characteristics of the level of "school maturity".

The teacher's communication with first graders is interrupted, and it is necessary to take into account the behavioral characteristics associated with the child's ability to communicate with adults and peers. Among first graders, the community has a high percentage of their children who experience all kinds of communication difficulties. This includes hypercommunicative children who interfere with the teacher's lesson and are also ashamed to respond, so that they leave taasurot, such as not knowing anything or not listening to what the teacher says. Both require different forms of loving and patient labor of the teacher.

The teacher's voice should be confidential and soft. An authoritarian style of communication between a teacher and first graders is unacceptable. Different forms cannot be ignored. Non-verbal communication-hug the child, take his hand, rub him over the head, touch him, etc. It not only calms the child, but also makes him feel confident that adults treat him well. Special attention should be paid to this rule, because, for a first grader, it is important for his teacher to have a kind, positive attitude towards him, which should not depend on the real success of the child.

The requirements for the fulfillment of school standards of behavior should be introduced gradually and not in the form of instructions, but in the form of desires.

Irritability, rude words cannot be accepted by the teacher. The necessary rule should be repeated over and over again with patience and tenderness.

To develop the independence and activity of children, it is important to positively assess each successful step of children, an attempt to independently find an answer to the question (the mistake is unsuccessful). It is very useful to give children creative educational assignments: to come up with something, guess, collect other examples, etc.k. To allow children to argue together with the teacher, think, make mistakes, find the right solution.

Children with low activity require special attention. The main task of the teacher is to stimulate any manifestation of the initiative, the desire to speak, answer the question and work on the board. It is very important to specially prepare such a child for the answer-to show his activities to the whole class, without fear of being too praised to stand by him. If the teacher is sure of the wrong answer, you should not rush to call the child to the board, it is better to allow the child to answer him “by ear” so as not to show his mistakes to the class.

In the first grade, children should be taught to organize their activities: plan their actions, change working conditions (for example, remove a textbook or notebook, put a letterbox, close a book, etc.k). this requires patient, long-term work, a step-by-step instruction, explaining in detail what and how to do (“opened the letter case”, “found a pocket for this letter”, “remove”, “close the case”).

A serious test for most children entering the first grade, which is associated with a sharp change in the whole way of life. They need to get used to the team, new requirements, daily commitments.

Cognitive activity is being formed, various types of memory, verbal-logical thinking are developing. High emotionality contributes to the predominance of involuntary reactions. But the teacher is consciously able to control his behavior, submit to the necessary requirements-an arbitrary development. At the age of primary school, children actively form an internal action plan, the ability to reflect begins to develop [5].

As a rule, children strive to become schoolchildren: they go to school with them, with great interest and preparation for execution, training assignments... but for many of them, the school requirements are very difficult, and the schedule is very tight. This period of adaptation to school for children can be traumatic.

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